

The Rates of Racemisation of Acids of the Type $R_1(R_2)CH\cdot COOH$.

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Acids of the type $R_1R_2CH\cdot COOH$ are readily racemised if R_1 and R_2 are aromatic groups but are racemised only with difficulty if one of the groups is aliphatic. Thus Kipping and Hunter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1009) showed that α -methyl- β -phenylpropionic acid was not at all readily racemised, while Rupe and Kerkovins (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1398) found that $\alpha\beta$ -diphenylpropionic acid was readily racemised and similar behaviour was observed by McKenzie and Widdows (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 702) in the case of phenyl-*p*-tolyl-acetic acid. We have prepared and examined acids of the type (I).

These acids readily undergo inversion at the α -carbon atom when R is $PhCH_2-$, $p\text{-}BrC_6H_4CH_2-$, or $PhCH_2CH_2-$, but not when R is Me or $n\text{-}Bu$ (Peacock and Menon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1296; 1935, 15). In the present paper the behaviour of acids of the type, $R R'CH\cdot COOH$ (II) is described.

The acids examined are:

- (1) α -Benzyl-*n*-caproic (II, $R=n\text{-}Bu$; $R'=PhCH_2$)
- (2) α -*p*-Bromobenzyl-*n*-caproic (II, $R=n\text{-}Bu$; $R'=p\text{-}BrC_6H_4CH_2$)
- (3) α -Benzyl- β -*p*-bromophenylpropionic (II, $R=PhCH_2$; $R'=p\text{-}BrC_6H_4CH_2$)
- (4) α -Benzyl- β -*m*-bromophenylpropionic (II, $R=PhCH_2$; $R'=m\text{-}BrC_6H_4CH_2$)
- (5) α -Benzyl- β -*p*-chlorophenylpropionic (II, $R=PhCH_2$; $R'=p\text{-}ClC_6H_4CH_2$)
- (6) α -Benzyl- β -*m*-chlorophenylpropionic (II, $R=PhCH_2$; $R'=m\text{-}ClC_6H_4CH_2$).

No systematic examination of acids of this type appears to have been made and the object of the present work was to

confirm the accelerative effect of aromatic groups and to search for an alternating effect by substituents in the aromatic nucleus. In the following table are given the times of half racemisation for these acids.

TABLE I.
Racemisation velocities.

Acid.	Half racemisation time.
α -Benzyl- <i>n</i> -caproic	18 hr. (approx.)
α - <i>p</i> -Bromobenzyl- <i>n</i> -caproic	18 (approx.)
α -Benzyl- β - <i>p</i> -bromophenylpropionic	1.5
α " " <i>m</i> - " "	1.0
α " " <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylpropionic	1.5
α " " <i>m</i> - " "	1.9

It will be seen that replacement of the *n*-butyl group by the benzyl or *p*-bromobenzyl group greatly increases the rate of racemisation. The first two acids were racemised so slowly that the rates are not accurate enough to decide whether the introduction of the bromine atom exerts any influence. Certainly any effect cannot be great. When the *para*-substituted acids are compared it is seen that chlorine and bromine exert similar effects but that with the halogen in the *meta*-position the bromo-acid racemises faster than the chloro-acids. Comparing the effect of each halogen in the *p*- and *m*-positions it is seen that with chlorine the *p*-acid reacts faster than the *m*-, while with bromine the *p*-acid reacts more slowly than the *m*-.

Kipping and Hunter (*loc. cit.*) suggested that the racemisation of α -substituted acids was due to enolisation:—

Gadamer (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1913, ii, 87, 312), who found that the ethyl ester of tropic acid was racemised more readily than the sodium salt, suggested that the α -hydrogen atom was ionised:—

and the ionised molecule then underwent racemisation. He pointed out that there was a causal relationship between the ionisability of

one of the groups attached to the asymmetric carbon atom and racemisation and that the α -H atom was able to be ionised owing to the negative character of the groups attached to the α -carbon atom. This explanation has been extended by Ingold and Wilson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 773) who found that the rate of racemisation of 2-*o*-carboxybenzylindan-1-one was very nearly equal to its rate of bromination. As the rate of the latter reaction is generally regarded as determined by the rate of expulsion of a proton, the approximate equality of the two rates of reaction supports the suggestion that both are determined by the ease of proton expulsion. Racemisation is thus a special case of proton tautomerism and is favoured by the entry of electron attracting groups (*cf.* Wilson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 98). The results described in this paper support this view; replacement of the butyl group by the more strongly electron attracting groups, benzyl or *p*-bromobenzyl, accelerates the rate of racemisation.

The halogenated acids can be considered from two points of view, firstly as affording data for a comparison of the effect of replacing chlorine by bromine and secondly as giving information as to the working and existence of an alternating effect. Replacement of bromine by chlorine in benzene derivatives does not always produce consistent results. *p*-Chloroaniline reacts faster than *p*-bromoaniline with both benzyl bromide and 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene (Peacock; Peacock and Attar Singh, unpublished data). Davies and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1601) observed similar effects with the substituted dimethylanilines. The reactivity of an amine is usually regarded as being increased by increased electron availability at the nitrogen atom so that in these cases the replacement of bromine by chlorine apparently increases electron availability at the *para*-position in the benzene ring. This conclusion is confirmed by the results obtained by Flürscheim (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 84) who showed that *p*-chloroaniline was a stronger base than *p*-bromoaniline. On the other hand Kuhn and Wassermann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 11, 31) showed that *p*-chlorobenzoic acid was a slightly stronger acid than *p*-bromobenzoic acid thus indicating that electron availability in the *p*-carboxyl group was less in the chloro-acid than the bromo as ionisation is favoured by electron attracting groups. Olivier (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1922, 41, 646; 1930, 49, 697) showed that *p*-chlorobenzyl chloride was hydrolysed more rapidly than *p*-bromobenzyl bromide; in this reaction electron accession to the carbon atom of the CH_2Cl group is

regarded as favouring reactivity so that here the replacement of bromine by chlorine favours electron availability at the *para*-position. Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1128) found similar results with aniline and pyridine with *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromobenzyl bromides. On the whole, therefore, the balance of evidence is in favour of the view that the replacement of bromine by chlorine helps electron availability at the *para*-position. The racemisation of the acids studied would be expected to be helped by electron recession, that is by decreased availability at the *para*-position. The chloro- and bromo-acids show no difference so that the difference in electron availability apparently fails to make itself felt at the distance of two carbon atoms. Dippy and Williams (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 162) similarly found almost no difference in the dissociation constants of the *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids where the ionisable hydrogen is also separated from *para*-carbon atom by two carbon atoms.

The alternating effect of these halogens is bound up with their electromeric effects which cause greater electron availability at the *para*-position than the *meta* and therefore greater reactivity at the *para*-position towards electron-seeking reagents. This conclusion is supported by the results obtained by Olivier (*loc. cit.*) who showed that *p*-chloro and *p*-bromobenzyl chlorides were hydrolysed more rapidly than the *meta*-compounds. The reactivity of the chlorine here is generally regarded as helped by electron accession to the CH_2Cl -group and therefore the *para*-halogen atom appears to favour electron accession to that group as compared with the halogen in the *meta*-position. A comparison of the rates of reaction of *m*- and *p*-chloro- and bromoanilines with benzyl bromide and with dinitrochlorbenzene confirms this conclusion; in all cases the *para*-halogenated amine reacts faster than the *meta*-compound. The racemisation of the acids considered would presumably be helped by electron recession and should, therefore, take place faster with the *meta*-halogen derivatives than with the *para*-compounds. This is true of the *m*- and *p*-bromo-acids but not of the chloro-acids. It is possible that the difference is due to the electromeric effect of bromine being greater than that of chlorine. The unshared electrons of the larger atom would be expected to be less firmly held than those of the smaller atom; it is this effect which is responsible for the greater electron availability in the *p*-position to the halogen than in the *m*- and, therefore, the difference in electron availability in the two positions would be expected to be greater in the case of bromine than in

the case of chlorine. This does not, however, explain why the opposite effect is observed in the case of chlorine which in this particular instance behaves as though the electromeric effect is absent. Further work is obviously necessary to support the superstructure of theory.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The acids were prepared and resolved by the methods described by Peacock and Menon (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 1, 407, 412). M/300 g. of each acid was dissolved in 13.25 c. c. of 1.007N-NaOH and made up to 100 c. c. The sodium salt was thus dissolved finally in N/10-NaOH solution. The initial rotation of the solution was taken and then it was heated to 100° in a boiling water-bath and samples withdrawn at regular intervals, cooled, and the rotations measured. In all cases the H_gyellow line was used. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Racemisation of Na- α -substituted β -phenylpropionates.
Ph·CH₂·CHR·COONa in N/10-NaOH at 100°.

Time.	R = <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ .	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ .	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ .	<i>m</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ .
	α	α	α	α
0	0.12°	0.10°	0.31°	0.185°
1 hr.	0.078°	0.07°	0.22°	0.102°
2	0.053°	0.055°	0.12°	0.06°
3	0.033°	0.035°	0.058°	0.032°
4	0.020°	0.030°	0.036°	0.020°
8			0.025°	

TABLE III.

Racemisation of Na- α -substituted hexoates
C₄H₉·CH(R)·COONa in N/10-NaOH at 100°.

Time.	R = <i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ .	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .
	α	α
0	0.50°	0.20°
1 hr.	0.45°	0.18°
2	0.46°	0.17°
3	0.45°	0.16°
4	0.44°	0.16°
8	0.42°	0.16°

We have to thank the University of Rangoon for a grant in aid of this investigation which is being continued.